

The New Expression of a Series in Mass-Energy Equivalence

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Abstract

This paper derives a series of the mass–energy equivalence in special relativity in a new way. The new equation indicates more accurately that energy distributes on various spheres that with different radii. The energy distributed on each sphere is proportional to the square of the sphere and is inversely proportional to the velocity of light sphere. Energy and velocity of the particle are proportionally associated while energy and mass are linearly associated. Based upon the study, possible future applications in the fields of particle acceleration are discussed as well.

Keywords: energy, mass, relativity, series, gravity

1. INTRODUCTION

According to classical mechanics, the kinetic energy of particle m is expressed by the following equation [1]:

$$E = \frac{1}{2}mv^2. \quad (1)$$

However, based on the special theory of relativity, equation (1) should be stated by the expression [1]:

$$E = \frac{mc^2}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}. \quad (2)$$

This is the famous Albert Einstein's mass–energy equivalence [2, pp.57-59], which indicates the relationship of energy and mass. And the equation (2) can be expressed by means of a series involved [1], namely the formula below:

$$E = mc^2 + m\frac{v^2}{2} + \frac{3}{8}m\frac{v^4}{c^2} + \dots \quad (3)$$

and more precisely it is:

$$E = mc^2 + \frac{1}{2}mv^2 + \frac{3}{8}m\frac{v^4}{c^2} + \frac{5}{16}m\frac{v^6}{c^4} + \frac{35}{128}m\frac{v^8}{c^6} + \frac{63}{256}m\frac{v^{10}}{c^8} + \dots \quad (4)$$

2. EQUATION DERIVATION

After a long time of studying the formula (4), by keeping the value conditions of the formula unchanged, we derived the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} E &= mc^2 + mv^2 \left[\frac{1}{2} + \frac{3}{8} \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} \right) + \frac{5}{16} \left(\frac{v^4}{c^4} \right) + \frac{35}{128} \left(\frac{v^6}{c^6} \right) + \frac{63}{256} \left(\frac{v^8}{c^8} \right) + \dots \right] \\ &= mc^2 + mv^2 \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} \right)^0 + \frac{3}{8} \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} \right)^1 + \frac{5}{16} \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} \right)^2 + \frac{35}{128} \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} \right)^3 + \frac{63}{256} \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} \right)^4 + \dots \right] \\ &= mv^2 \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} \right)^{-1} + mv^2 \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} \right)^0 + \frac{3}{8} \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} \right)^1 + \frac{5}{16} \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} \right)^2 + \frac{35}{128} \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} \right)^3 + \frac{63}{256} \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} \right)^4 + \dots \right] \\ &= mv^2 \left[\left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} \right)^{-1} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} \right)^0 + \frac{3}{8} \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} \right)^1 + \frac{5}{16} \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} \right)^2 + \frac{35}{128} \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} \right)^3 + \frac{63}{256} \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} \right)^4 + \dots \right] \\ &= mv^2 \left[\left(\frac{4\pi v^2}{4\pi c^2} \right)^{-1} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{4\pi v^2}{4\pi c^2} \right)^0 + \frac{3}{8} \left(\frac{4\pi v^2}{4\pi c^2} \right)^1 + \frac{5}{16} \left(\frac{4\pi v^2}{4\pi c^2} \right)^2 + \frac{35}{128} \left(\frac{4\pi v^2}{4\pi c^2} \right)^3 + \frac{63}{256} \left(\frac{4\pi v^2}{4\pi c^2} \right)^4 + \dots \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

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3. CONCLUSION

From the final line it can be viewed that equation (5) indicates the status of energy during the conversion process of mass and energy as well as the physical significance more definite. On the basis of equation (5), we arrived at the following preliminary conclusions:

- 3.1. The $4\pi v^2$ in equation (5) represents a sphere whose radius is v . This indicates that energy distributes on various spheres with different radii values. And the $4\pi c^2$ stands for a sphere whose radius is the velocity of light c .
- 3.2. The energy distributed on each sphere is proportional to the square value of the sphere and is inversely proportional to the velocity of light sphere $4\pi c^2$.
- 3.3. The energy of the velocity of light sphere $4\pi c^2$ is the maximum value.
- 3.4. The energy of the sphere is exponentially decreases with the growth of terms.
- 3.5. Energy and velocity of the particle are proportionally associated while the energy and mass are linearly associated. Moreover it indicates that matter (mass is the measurement unit) and motions (energy is the measurement unit) are inseparable.

Furthermore, we studied more comprehensively about the gravitation formula [2, p.5]:

$$F = G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^2}. \quad (6)$$

It can be deduced that gravity obeys as well the same principle that energy distributes on various spheres in light of the mass-energy equivalence in special relativity. Thus, multiply distance squared r^2 by 4π as well as multiply the gravitational constant G by 4π , then the equation below can be obtained:

$$F = G \frac{4\pi m_1 m_2}{4\pi r^2}. \quad (7)$$

Here, we defined $G \times 4\pi$ in equation (7) as the gravitational constant Q . Thus, the gravitation formula can be expressed by the new form:

$$F = Q \frac{m_1 m_2}{4\pi r^2}. \quad (8)$$

The physical significance of the new expression (8) is it suggests the relationship between gravity and energy more clearly. From the above it can be observed that the value of gravity is inversely proportional to distance squared and the cause of which lies in gravity, the same as energy, can also distribute on the sphere whose radius is value r . Therefore, as the value r increases the square of the sphere becomes larger and larger, on the contrary, the energy becomes lower and lower, thus the gravity becomes lower and lower.

4. DISCUSSION

Modern high-energy particle accelerators can accelerate particles to the speed that is close to the speed of light. The speed of particle which is accelerated can be calculated more accurately by applying our new equation. In addition, the new equation serves as well in computing the change of energy more precisely based upon comparing the change of mass and the speed of particle at two different speed status.

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